

SYSTEM OF METHODS FOR FORMING STUDENTS' CREATIVE COMPETENCE AND ITS ASSESSMENT INDICATORS

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ANNOTATION: Creativity competence is an important part of preparing everyone in today's world to cooperate harmoniously, solve problems and search for new solutions. Developing creativity in students leads them to think critically, manage problems, seek new ideas, and innovate. In this article, we will talk about the system of methods aimed at forming students' creativity competence and its evaluation indicators.

KEY WORDS: creativity, assessment, independent thought, approaches, ability, ability, research, analysis, creative tasks

INTRODUCTION

Creative competence is the most basic and active form of manifestation of independent thinking qualities in a person. Despite the fact that all tariffs differ sharply from each other, it is possible to point out some common aspects. Firstly, the quality of the product obtained as a result of creative competence should be innovative; secondly, that these aspects were not present in the initial foundations of creative competence; and thirdly, any activity of creative competence is determined by the fact that it requires intellectual research.

Creative activity is complicated by insufficient psychological preparation of teachers and students for this process. Relying on a certain method, form, and means on a regular basis leads to the inability to adapt to new situations and the inability to work in unexpected situations. As a psychological condition, this can be manifested in various forms, including: not accepting the opinions and

opinions of others at all; strict defense of the generally accepted point of view; applying old methods to new content and tools; preservation of old methods in new methods; such as using traditional methods to solve a completely new problem.

Two interrelated tasks should be taken into account when organizing students' creative competence activities. The first of them is the development of students' independent thinking in the activity of creative competence, their eagerness to acquire knowledge, and the formation of their scientific worldview; the second is determined by teaching to independently apply acquired knowledge in education and practical activities.

MAIN PART

Creativity is the ability of people to express themselves, solve problems creatively, find new approaches and communicate their ideas to others. Developing creativity in students is one of the most important tasks, and there are various methods and assessment indicators to achieve this goal.

First, critical exercises, experiments, and laboratory work are common to develop creativity in students. Students should be given the opportunity to seek their own opinions on the most important and important questions, to use reasoning and to express themselves through physical and mental activities.

Second, it is important to organize gatherings for learning group work and management activities in order to provide students with the opportunity to explain their thoughts to each other during the educational process and to ensure their rapid development. By working in a group, students benefit from each other's ideas and have the opportunity to find and share new approaches.

A third method is to inspire students and develop their creativity by bringing them to learning activities in natural environments, such as nature or an art gallery. A natural environment can help students think, focus, and understand the most basic laws of nature.

Practical assessment indicators are also important for assessing creativity in students. Accepting advice and feedback, sharing ideas with other students, and being active in the community play a big role in improving students' creativity.

Acquaintance with scientific and technical information plays an important role in the development of creative competence. It serves as an important resource for providing readers with newsletters, information on scientific terms, and information on invention and patent science materials. Close cooperation with experts in the field of information technology and patent studies, regular familiarization with periodicals related to these fields will give positive results.

It requires the formation of an important source of innovative ideas and technologies in qualified students, along with the training of creative specialists. In this work, the concept of creative competence was adopted as an activity process aimed at creating a product of creative competence as an intellectual property based on the integration of knowledge, skills and abilities of students with scientific and technical knowledge and education-science-production.

In order to form and evaluate creativity competence, the unique characteristics of each student should be developed. It is aimed at students' ability to act in accordance with economic, social and personal requirements, solve problems, search for new solutions and create products and services that include the implementation of other innovative activities. The following techniques and pointers can help you develop creativity:

1. Research methods:

- To teach students to advance to express their opinions, to search for problems and to search for news.

- Ask creative questions to get students to create questions, find solutions to problems and issues.

2. Group work:

- Teaching students to work in groups, share ideas and work with a team.

- Development of social relations of students by organizing team activities.

3. Projects and practices:

- To guide students to create projects with their own ideas.
- Implementation of theoretical knowledge through practices and creating opportunities for students to create products.

4. Orienting students to creative thinking:

- To support students in expressing their ideas, developing new ideas and in their own self-management.
- Creation of a system of support and assessment of creative ideas.

5. Educational programs and technologies:

- Development of students' creativity by supporting interactive educational programs and technologies.
- Enable students to work on their practice and ideas through virtual labs, online resources and demonstrations.

6. Comparison and sharing of good practices among students:

- Comparing and sharing good practices among students helps each other learn to think creatively.

7. Evaluation indicators:

- Development of evaluation system for level of creativity, products and ideas.
- Supporting students' assessment indicators for their own practice, teamwork and other creative activities.

These methods and pointers can help students to improve their creativity competence. Teaching students to express themselves, ask questions, work in a team and search for information is a key part of learning, creativity and innovation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the system of methods and evaluation indicators aimed at the formation of creativity competence is to enable students to create creative ideas, work with problems, and find new solutions.

This system allows students to practice, exchange skills through group work, theoretical and practical exercises, develop community spirit through distance learning methods, and create ideas in situations that call for problem solving. Assessment indicators include student creativity, problem-solving experiences, and terms for experiential learning. These indicators make it possible to more clearly assess the level of creativity and creative approach of students.

In general, the system of methods and evaluation indicators aimed at the formation of creativity competence creates opportunities for students to master, apply a practical approach and strive to work with creative problems, and serves to develop their level of creativity.

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